

Enhancing piezoresistive sensitivity of PEDOT:PSS-based strain sensors through nickel microparticles incorporation.

Rehab Ramadan ^{1,2,3,*} and Raúl J. Martín-Palma ^{2,3}

¹ Department of Physics, Faculty of Science, Minia University, Minia 61519, Egypt

² Departamento de Física Aplicada, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain

³ Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales Nicolás Cabrera, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, 28049 Madrid, Spain

*Correspondence: rehabramadan@mu.edu.eg

Abstract

The present work discusses the fabrication and development of a piezoresistive strain sensor with remarkable sensitivity. The sensor is made up of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) and has a layer of interconnected Ni microparticles (NiMPs) on its surface. The elasticity of the PEDOT:PSS membrane is increased by the addition of polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). The piezoresistive strain sensor, comprising PEDOT:PSS, PVA, and NiMPs, was studied to determine its electrical signal, stability, and response time at various strains and bending angles. The applied strains ranged from 0% to 28%, which is a typical interval of human body movements. The experimental results prove that the sensors have exceptional performance compared to other strain sensors based on PEDOT:PSS.

Keywords: piezoresistive strain sensors; PEDOT:PSS; Ni microparticles ; human motion detection;

Introduction

Flexible and stretchable materials are increasingly being used for several technological applications and impact our daily lives. More specifically, flexible materials are used in electronics [1-4], energy storage applications [5-7], healthcare and biomedical applications [8-10]. These could also be used in human motion detection.

Flexible strain sensors are devices that show a change in their electrical or optical response in response to applied strains, including force, pressure, tension, weight,...etc [11]. A host of different methods are used for the fabrication of flexible materials, including, coating

34 techniques [12, 13], liquid phase mixing [14, 15], vacuum filtration methods [16], transferring
35 and cost-effective blending methods [17], printing technologies [18, 19], chemical synthesis
36 methods [20], and so forth. According to the working principle and the function of the
37 fabricated stretchable/conductive strain sensor, these can be classified into piezoelectric,
38 piezoresistive and capacitive strain sensors [21]. Among them, piezoresistive strain sensors are
39 widely used due to its simplicity in fabrication, low cost, and notable response at infinitesimal
40 action [22].

41 To meet the growing demand, the fabricated stretchable/conductor strain sensors should
42 undergo the crucial requirements to meet the human skin, clothes or footwears. Strain sensors
43 which undergo flexibility, stretching, soft, repeatability and stability are ideal for this purpose.
44 Generally, the structure and formation of outstanding strain sensors are classified into two
45 strategies [23, 24]:

46 (1) A mixture of the elastomer and the conducting material, where the conducting
47 material is embedded inside the elastomer [25-28]. In this case, the conducting material may
48 be in the form of a conducting polymer, or metallic micro/nanostructures.

49 (2) Growth of the conducting material on the surface of the elastomer [29-31]. In this
50 case, the growth of the active layer can be through the direct coating (e.g. spin coating, dip-
51 coating, spray coating, infiltration, printing) or deposition by vacuum systems.

52

53 Embedding of the conducting material in the elastomer is suitable for the fabrication of a
54 relatively thick sensor. However, the bonding interaction between the conducting material and
55 the elastomer becomes weaker at high stretching, which may cause delamination and vacancies
56 inside the elastomer [22]. Moreover, difficulty to perform ordered nanostructures inside the
57 elastomer. While the growth of the conducting structure on the surface of the elastomer is
58 suitable for the implementation of ordered nanostructures or homogeneous thin film. As a
59 result, stability in the performance of the sensor over cycling after stretching-
60 relaxing/compression-relaxing cycles.

61

62 Intrinsically conducting polymers are commonly used for stretchable/conducting strain sensors
63 due to their good processability, cost-effectiveness, tunable electrical properties [32]. For
64 instance, poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS), polypyrrole
65 (PPy) and polyaniline (PANI). However, these materials cannot serve as smart strain sensors
66 without the aid of elastomers to meet the demand of stretchability and flexibility. There are
67 natural polymers or products usually used as matrix or substrate for the stretchable strain sensor

68 because of their flexibility, stretchability, and durability. Including, poly (dimethyl siloxane)
69 (PDMS), isoprene rubber (IR), thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA)
70 and poly (styrene-butadiene-styrene) (SBS).

71
72 Herein, we present a highly sensitive and stretchable conducting strain sensors fabricated using
73 a rather simple and cost-effective strategy. For the first time, high-performance piezoresistive
74 strain sensors were developed by the distribution of magnetic nickel microparticles (NiMPs)
75 on a flat surface using a magnetic bar and then pouring of PEDOT:PSS flexible/stretchable
76 conducting polymer until it dries. The performed PEDOT:PSS conducting polymer was mixed
77 with PVA as a matrix material to give a large degree of flexibility and elasticity suitable for all
78 human motions. The Ni microparticles layer was then stuck to the surface of PEDOT:PSS
79 membrane, resulting in a composite of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs piezoresistive strain sensors
80 that are suitable for detecting a wide range of human motions. The current work is our first
81 attempt to work with magnetic particles in this context. In a future step, we plan on using
82 different magnetic particles including iron, cobalt, steel, or manganese.

83

84 **Experimental**

85 **Materials**

86 Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):polystyrene sulfonate PEDOT:PSS 1.3 wt%) was
87 purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) (99.5%), glycol alcohol, poly
88 vinyl alcohol (PVA), isopropanol alcohol (IPA), deionized water, nickel microparticles (1-5
89 μm , diameter)

90 **Preparation of PEDOT:PSS/PVA composite**

91 Poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) is an aqueous solution
92 with low viscosity. Stretchable membranes based on PEDOT:PSS need the addition of a
93 suitable elastomer to PEDOT:PSS to be suitable for piezoresistive devices. PVA is a water-
94 soluble and biocompatible elastomer. For that, a composite of PEDOT:PSS and PVA
95 (PEDOT:PSS/PVA) at adequate amounts is suitable for performing flexible and stretchable
96 membranes.

97

98 The main requirement of the intended membrane is maintaining the good electrical conduction
99 properties of PEDOT:PSS in addition to the flexibility and stretching of the membrane, For

100 that, the amount of PVA was optimized to be 5.7% compared to PEDOT:PSS solution.
101 Accordingly, 14 ml of PEDOT:PSS solution was mixed with 2 ml Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)
102 (99.5%) and 0.1 ml glycol alcohol. DMSO and glycol alcohol assisted in improving the
103 electrical conduction of PEDOT:PSS[33]. In another container, 0.8 gm of PVA powder was
104 mixed with 9.2 ml deionized water and stirred on a magnetic stirrer at 95°C until complete
105 dissolving of the powder and getting a clear gel. Afterwards, the PVA solution was mixed with
106 the PEDOT:PSS solution and stirred at high speed for 10 minutes for complete dissolution.
107 Moreover, 0.1 ml HCl was added to the composite and the mixture was maintained in a
108 sonicator for another 10 minutes.

109

110 Flexible and stretchable membrane of the conductive PEDOT:PSS/PVA were obtained by
111 pouring 7 ml of the composite in a petri-dish of 3 cm diameter and left in ambient air for two
112 days for complete drying from the residual solvents. According to the data recorded, the
113 thickness of the PEDOT:PSS/PVA membrane was 500 μm . It was measured by means of a
114 digital micrometer. The resulting membrane was cut in $1 \times 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces. Afterwards, two
115 rectangular pieces of copper tap were fixed at each edge of PEDOT:PSS/PVA sample for the
116 electrical measurements. To prevent the samples from the environment effects, transparent
117 elastomer of polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was poured on the surface of the
118 PEDOT:PSS/PVA membrane to prevent NiMPs from oxidation. Figure 1 shows the schematic
119 representation of the preparation steps of the flexible pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA membranes
120 and a picture of the resulted pristine membrane after getting out from the Petri dish.

121

122

123 **Figure 1.** Schematic representation of the preparation steps for the fabrication of the flexible
124 membranes based on PEDOT:PSS/PVA and a real image of the membrane bended.

125

126 Ni-microparticles treatments

127

128 Ni microparticles (NiMPs) with diameters between 1 and 5 μm were used to improve the
129 electrical conduction and piezoresistive properties of the PEDOT:PSS/PVA composite. The
130 NiMPs were subjected to multiple cleaning steps before being used. The multi-cleaning steps
131 is very important for etching the oxide layer on its surface to be suitable for improving the
132 electrical conduction of PEDOT:PSS/PVA membranes. Firstly, an amount of NiMPs were
133 rinsed in HF (48%):H₂O (1:20 V) mixture for 20 seconds to remove the oxide layer. Next, the
134 particles were rinsed in IPA path several times then washing in a sonicator for 15 minutes. The
135 IPA solution was replaced several times to confirm the absence of any residuals of HF acid.
136 Consequently, the particles were dried slowly on a hot plate at 40°C for 10 minutes. 0.5 gm of
137 NiMPs were uniformly distributed on the bottom of 3-cm diameter petri dish using a magnetic
138 stirring bar magnet. The magnet was placed horizontally on the back side of the petri dish and
139 moved regularly up and down to yield a uniform distribution of the NiMPs inside the petri dish.
140 Afterwards, 7 ml of the previously prepared PEDOT:PSS/PVA composite was poured slowly
141 over the distributed NiMPs in the petri dish. The sample was left in ambient air for two days

142 to let the residual solvents evaporate. As a consequence, flexible and stretchable membranes
 143 composed of PEDOT:PSS, PVA and NiMPs (PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs) were obtained.
 144 Similarly, the membrane was cut into (1×1.5 cm²) rectangles. Afterwards, two rectangular
 145 pieces of copper tap were fixed at each edge of PEDOT:PSS/PVA sample for the electrical
 146 measurements. Besides, a transparent elastomer of PDMS was poured on the surface of the
 147 PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs membrane and left to dry as a preserving layer. The obtained
 148 membranes of pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA and PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs were kept in a
 149 desiccator to conserve the flexible and stretching properties. Figure 2 shows the cleaning steps
 150 of the NiMPs and the subsequent formation of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs membranes.

151

152

153 **Figure 2.** Schematic representation of the processing steps for the cleaning procedure of NiMPs and
 154 preparation steps of the modified flexible membrane of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs.

155

156 Furthermore, Figure 3 indicates the structure of the modified PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs strain
 157 sensors due to stretching and releasing or bending effects. As indicated, the distance between
 158 the NiMPs increases with stretching and returns to the interconnected state upon being released.
 159 As a result, change in the electrical conduction happens with the mechanical deformation.
 160 Additionally, Figure 3.I shows actual images of the sensor after applying different strains using
 161 the homemade holder and Figure 3.II portrays bending of the sensor at various angles in the
 162 forward and reverse directions.

166 **Figure 3.** Schematic representation of the performance of the fabricated PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs strain sensor
 167 due to mechanical effects. I- Real images of stretching and releasing effects and II- real images of bending effect
 168 at different angles.

170 **Characterization techniques**

172 The morphology of the pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA membrane and PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs
173 membrane was studied by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) using a JSM-
174 IT200 microscope operated at 20 kV. The morphology was analyzed under different strains to
175 determine the distribution of NiMPs upon stretching.

176

177 The electrical measurements of the fabricated strain sensors were carried out in a BioLogic SP-
178 150 potentiostat. Measuring the electrical response as a function of applied strains was studied
179 using a homemade holder. The holder was performed using 3-D printer. Table 1 indicates the
180 names of the strains and the corresponding values. Current-voltage (I-V) curves were obtained
181 at a scan rate 10 mV/s and applied potential in the 0 V to +0.5 V range. I-V curves were
182 obtained as a function of strains and bending angles.

183

184 **Table 1.** Names of strain and the corresponding values.

Name of strain	Value of strain (%)
No strain	0
Strain 1	4
Strain 2	8
Strain 3	12
Strain 4	16
Strain 5	20
Strain 6	24
Strain 7	28

185

186 **Results and discussions**

187

188 **Morphology**

189

190 Figure 4 portrays the morphology and structure of the surface of the fabricated pristine
191 PEDOT:PSS/PVA sensors and modified one by NiMPs. Figure 4.(a) shows the homogeneity
192 and smoothness of the pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA composite. Distributing the magnetic NiMPs
193 by the bar magnet leads to the interconnection of the microparticles on the surface of
194 PEDOT:PSS/PVA composite at 0% strain. In Figure 4.(b), it is clear from the highlighted area

195 marked in yellow that the NiMPs interconnected and performed larger particles after sticking
196 to PEDOT:PSS/PVA membrane at 0% strain. Figure 4.(b) confirms the combination of the
197 microparticles in a good performance and stability on its place leading to completely covering
198 of the PEDOT:PSS/PVA membrane with the NiMPs. This combination between the
199 microparticles contributed to obtaining a remarkable electrical conduction of the piezoresistive
200 sensor at 0% strain. Probably due to the small size of the NiMPs, (1-5 μm diameter) and
201 flexibility of the membranes. Stretching of the sensor leads to the creation of free parts between
202 NiMPs on the surface of the PEDOT:PSS/PVA membrane . Figures 4.(c) and 4.(d) show a
203 larger distance at higher strains, 12% to 24% as highlighted by the red arrows. The increase in
204 the stretching effect enhances the ability to determine the shape and size of the contributed
205 NiMPs. It was determined that the diameter of the NiMPS falls within the range of 1 to 5 μm
206 using the ImageJ software. In the following electrical section, we will notice the notable
207 reduction in the electrical conduction due to the stretching of the modified sensors. This
208 behavior contributed to enhancing the gauge factor of the modified sensors.

209

210 **Figure 4. (a)** Top-view FESEM images of pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA sensor. **(b), (c), and (d)**
211 FESEM images of modified PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs piezoresistive sensors at 0%, 12% and
212 24% strains, respectively.

213

214 **Electrical response of modified piezoresistive sensors**

215

216 **Effect of strain**

217

218 PEDOT:PSS is a conducting polymeric material composed of two chains, namely a PSS-rich
219 component and a PEDOT-rich one. PEDOT:PSS is an electrolyte incorporating conducting
220 conjugated PEDOT with positive charges and insulating PSS with negative charges [34]. The
221 mechanical effect on this polymer causes a relaxation of the chains without a change in its
222 electrical conduction properties [35-37]. Accordingly, the current-voltage curves were
223 measured for pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA membranes at different strain levels. The
224 experimental results are shown in Figure 5.a. The values of the electrical current indicate the
225 good electrical conduction of the fabricated pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA flexible membranes.
226 Moreover, the change in the electrical conduction is not noticeable due to strain. This behavior
227 is attributed to the unique distribution of the components of the polymer after stretching. Only
228 expanding in the length of the chains takes place as shown in the schematic graph in Figure 3.
229 This property encourages researchers to use this polymer in flexible electronic devices due to
230 its electrical stability with bending or stretching effects [34].

232

233 **Figure 5. (a)** I-V curves for pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA flexible membrane at different strains. **(b)** I-V curves for
 234 flexible PEDOT:PSS/PVA combined with NiMPs under the effect of different strains. **(c)** The behavior of the
 235 electrical resistance with the increase in strain levels of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs flexible strain sensors. **(d)**
 236 Fitting of two linear regions from the relation between $\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}$ and $\Delta \varepsilon$ to obtain GFs for PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs
 237 flexible sensors.

238

239 However, combining PEDOT:PSS with other conducting materials composed of micro- or
 240 nano-structures leads to a notable change in their electrical conduction due to mechanical
 241 effects. Figure S1 in the supplementary materials shows the linear relation between applied
 242 stress and strain for the modified PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs sensor in the range of human
 243 motions. The proportional amount between stress and strain is known as Young's modulus,
 244 which equals 4.15 MPa in the case of our sensor. Thus, the combined structures can be used in
 245 wearable and body-sensing applications [38-40]. In this line, Figure 5.b shows the effect of
 246 strain on the electrical conduction of the modified PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs flexible sensors.
 247 The inset figure shows the I-V curve at 0% strain. An outstanding response is observed due to

248 strain in the electrical conduction of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs membranes. The applied strain
249 typically is in the 0% to 28% range. The maximum value of strain is less than 30%, which is
250 the highest value of strain that can be achieved from the movement of human body parts. The
251 experimental results indicate a reduction in electrical conduction with increasing elongation.
252 The reduced electrical conduction of the flexible strain sensor is attributed to increased distance
253 between the Ni microparticles with increasing strain value. Combining flexible conducting
254 polymer with metallic particles results in an effective piezoresistive strain sensor with a
255 remarkable electrical response.

256

257 Regarding the electrical response of pristine PEDOT:PSS/PVA and PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs
258 at 0% strain, the results indicate that the establishment of combined PEDOT:PSS with metallic
259 microparticles flexible sensor made a meaningful contribution to the extraordinary electrical
260 response as shown in Figures 5.c and 5.d. Probably, this response is attributed to the distribution
261 of the metallic nickel microparticles on the surface of PEDOT:PSS flexible membrane in an
262 agglomerated form as indicated from FESEMS images, (Figure 4.(b)).

263

264 As depicted in Figure 5.d, a remarkable response of the fabricated strain sensor is due to
265 applying small strain values. The electrical resistance increases from tens of Ohms at 0% strain
266 to thousands at 28%. This behavior indicates the notable response by combining PEDOT:PSS
267 with metallic Ni particles. The relative resistance changes during the stretching process can be
268 used to express the sensitivity of the strain sensors by the gauge factor (GF) values.
269 Accordingly, GF values were calculated based on the following equation:

$$270 \quad GF = \frac{\Delta R}{R_0} / \Delta \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

$$271 \quad \Delta \varepsilon = \frac{\Delta L}{L_0} \quad (2)$$

272 where ΔR refers to the resistance difference before and after stretching, R_0 refers to the initial
273 resistance before stretching, $\Delta \varepsilon$ is the applied strain, ΔL is the length difference before and after
274 stretching and L_0 is the initial length of the flexible membrane.

275

276 In our study, the quick response to the mechanical stimuli and the random distribution of nickel
277 microparticles on the surface of PEDOT:PSS polymeric membrane leads to no-linear relation
278 between the obtained resistance difference and the employed strains. Figure 5.d indicates a

279 linear fitting in two regions with two GFs. At lower strain values, the GF is 1682. Besides, the
280 increase in the strain levels leads to a higher value of GF equals 5951. The notable increase in
281 the GF at high strain values is related to the immense difference in the electrical resistance due
282 to broadening the distance between nickel microparticles with stretching. Comparing our
283 results of GFs with the previously reported studies on PEDOT:PSS strain sensors, we conclude
284 the outstanding performance of the implemented PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs sensor, shown in
285 Table 2. Accordingly, combining PEDOT:PSS and the interconnected metallic particles on the
286 surface is appropriate for human motion detection applications.

287 **Table 2.** Different structures of piezoresistive strain sensors based on the conducting PEDOT:PSS polymer.

Structure	Gauge factor	Reference
PEDOT:PSS was grown on Silicone flexible substrate	6.9	[41]
A conductive polymer (PEDOT:PSS) thin film deposited on a flexible substrate of polyimide using a peeling technique.	17.8	[42]
polymeric nanofibrous composite of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) elastomer and conductive 7: PSS polymer	20	[43]
PEO/PEDOT:PSS Electrospun Nanofibers (The nanostructured active layer based on a blend of poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO) and PEDOT:PSS	45.84 in traction and 208.55 in compression mode	[44]
A microchannel based ultrasensitive strain sensor was developed using conductive PEDOT: PSS	280	[45]
poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene): poly(4-styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS) modified layered double hydroxides (LDHs) suspensions.	2326.84	[46]
conductive whisker carbon nanotube (CNT) film filled with PEDOT:PSS	4839	[47]
Nanohybrid structure of (polyurethane) PU-PEDOT:PSS/ SWCNT/PU-PEDOT:PSS	837.1	[48]
PEDOT:PSS polymer microchannel (diameter $\approx 175 \mu\text{m}$) based stretchable strain sensor	12000	[49]
Composite of PEDOT:PSS mixed with PVA polymers and NiMPs were dispersed on the surface using a magnetic bar.	1582 at low strain levels and 5951 at higher strain	Present work

291

292 The sensitivity of strain sensors due to bending demonstrates the potential applications in
293 wearable devices. Figure 6.a shows the current-voltage curves of the PEDOT:PSS/NiMPs
294 strain sensor due to bending at different angles. Herein, curving at 45° leads to the best
295 electrical response. This behavior is attributed to narrowing the distance between NiMPs due
296 to bending. While bending at 225° in the reverse direction leads to a decrease in the obtained
297 electrical current because of the increase in the distance between NiMPs. Accordingly, Figure
298 6.b summarizes the relationship between the obtained electrical current at 0.5V and bending
299 angles. As a result, the implemented strain sensor can be applied for human motion detection
300 like bending of arms, fingers, knees, and feet. Besides, the detection of facial expressions and
301 breathing rate. Herein, the bending effects were performed manually to meet the necessity for
302 dynamic human motion detection.

303

304 **Figure 6.** (a) I-V curves of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs sensor as a function of bending angles. (b) chart of current
 305 values at different bending angles. (c) relation between logarithmic impedance and frequency at different bending
 306 angles. (d) Current-voltage (ON/OFF) response during bending of the device at 90° and without bending. (e) I-
 307 V curve of PEDOT:PSS/PVA/NiMPs membrane during cycling between bending ON at 90° and OFF. (f) the
 308 response of the device at one cycle between ON and OFF to estimate the response and releasing time of the sensor.

309

310 Additionally, Figure 6.c presents the logarithmic electrical resistance response in a wide
311 frequency range. As depicted, the resistance increases with increasing frequency. This behavior
312 may be related to the disability of charge carriers to follow the electrical signal with increasing
313 the frequency.

314

315 Repeatability and reproducibility are additional analyses essential for the evaluation of the
316 performance of strain sensors for practical use. As indicated in Figure 6.d, the fabricated strain
317 sensor responds to the applied bending effect with increasing biasing realistically. As shown,
318 bending at 90° (ON) leads to higher values of the electrical current than the straight position
319 (OFF). This behaviour is attributed to a reduced distance between the metallic NiMPs upon
320 bending. Besides, Figure S2 shows cycling between bending ON/OFF of the strain sensor at
321 0.35V biasing. The figure indicated the stability of the device over cycling up to 1000 cycles.
322 This stable behavior of the performed device demonstrates that the NiMPs are fixed on the
323 surface of the PEDOT:PSS membrane. The used composite of PEDOT:PSS and PVA polymers
324 can return to its initial length after stretching and releasing modes several times. More clearly,
325 Figure 6.e shows the response of cycling at a small region. Likewise, the response and releasing
326 times can be obtained from one cycle, indicated in Figure 6.f. The calculated response time is
327 almost 1.0 s, while releasing time is 1.25 s. Remarkably, the fast response of the modified strain
328 sensors based on PEDOT:PSS with NiMPs on its surface reveals the truth of our anticipation
329 about using it in subtle and drastic human motion detection. For that, a real test of our modified
330 device was done on human finger's motion as shown in Figure S3 in the supplementary
331 materials. The figures portray the good response of the sensor to human's finger motion
332 between bending and releasing and twisting of the sensor in a homogenous manner.

333

334 **Conclusions**

335 Highly sensitive and effective flexible, stretchable piezoresistive strain sensors suitable for the
336 future development human motion detections were fabricated by a very simple and costless
337 method. The high-performance piezoresistive strain sensors were fabricated by the growth of
338 a thin layer of nickel microparticles (NiMPs) on the surface of the PEDOT:PSS
339 flexible/stretchable conducting polymer. The combination of the microparticles in a good
340 performance and stability in its place contributed to obtaining remarkable electrical conduction
341 of the piezoresistive sensor at 0% strain.

342

343 The experimental results show a reduction in the electrical conductivity with increasing
344 elongation. The reduced electrical conduction of the flexible strain sensor is attributed to the
345 increased distance between the Ni microparticles with increasing strain value. It is noticeable
346 that the electrical resistance increases from tens of Ohms at 0% strain to thousands at 28%.
347 This behavior indicates the notable response by combining PEDOT:PSS with metallic Ni
348 particles.

349

350 Furthermore, the sensitivity of strain sensors due to bending effects was studied at different
351 angles. Herein, curving at 45° represents the best electrical response. This behavior is attributed
352 to narrowing the distance between NiMPs due to bending. While bending at 225° in the reverse
353 direction leads to a decrease in the obtained electrical current because of the increase in the
354 distance between NiMPs. Moreover, the cycling of the modified sensor was tested at different
355 voltages. The results indicated the fast response of the device and the notable electrical
356 response increase with increasing voltage. Likewise, the response and releasing times are
357 almost 1.0 s and 1.25 s, respectively. Remarkably, the fast response of the modified strain
358 sensors based on PEDOT:PSS with NiMPs on its surface reveals the truth of our anticipation
359 about using it in subtle and drastic human motion detection. Moreover, detection of deformation
360 in civil infrastructures (bridges, etc.), wings of planes, other vehicles.

361

362 **AUTHOR DECLARATIONS**

363

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369

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371

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373 investigation (lead); methodology (lead); project administration (equal); visualization (lead);
374 resources (lead); writing – original draft (lead); writing – review and editing (equal). **R. J.**
375 **Martin-Palma:** formal analysis (supporting); project administration (equal); supervision
376 (lead); visualization (supporting); writing – review and editing (equal).

377

378 **Data availability:** The data that support the findings of this study are available from the
379 corresponding author upon reasonable request.
380

381

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